

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“EACH OTHER”

we hold our hands
as soon as the first light
of the new day glistens

we walk through alleys and roads
meeting strangers
dressed for every occasion

we cross bridges
where clear and dark waters
mirror our moods we share altogether

we observe lazily the midday sky
unmindful that everyone across the way
caught in the turmoil of a busy life

we visit places we always dream
defining ourselves
and knowing who we really are
if we are for each other

but as soon as
the last gleaming light
touches between us
your hands are still there
holding me all the time